

Impact of CPNS Latsar on Changes in Behavioral Attitudes of Latsar Participants for the 4th Kerinci District in 2021

Asnofidal¹, Hamid Majid²

¹Widyaiswara Main Expert BPSDM Jambi Province, Jambi, Indonesia

²Widyaiswara BPSDM Provinsi Jambi, Jambi, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Basic Training (Latsar) for Prospective Civil Servants is important to prepare civil servants who have integrity, professionalism, neutrality, independence, and are free from political interference, as well as the ability to provide good public services to the community. For this reason, this study aims to see the impact of the CPNS Latsar on the attitudes and behavior of Latsar Batch 4 Kerinci Regency participants in 2021 which is measured through the basic values of civil servants (ANEKA). The research method used is a mixed research *method*, namely qualitative and quantitative. The subjects of the study were CPNS Latsar participants who were appointed to 4 Kerinci districts in 2021 with 181 participants and the head of the Latsar work unit within the Kerinci district. Instruments of data collection were done through interview guide sheets, observation sheets, questionnaire sheets, and test sheets for CPNS Latsar participants. Quantitative data collection techniques were carried out through pretest and posttest activities. Furthermore, qualitative data was collected through open questionnaires and interviews with the leaders of the Latsar participants after they returned to their respective work environments. Quantitative analysis was carried out by analyzing before and after the implementation of Basic Training (Latsar) through the independent *simple t test method*. Meanwhile, qualitative data analysis was carried out through triangulation which consisted of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. To see how much influence Latsar activities have on changes in participants' attitudes and behavior, the N-gain test is carried out. The findings of the study indicate that there is a significant effect on the implementation of CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) on the attitudes and behavior of Latsar 4 Kerinci Regency participants in 2021. This is confirmed by the t-test values for the 5 ANEKA values variables which show scores below 0, 05. CPNS Latsar activities have a good impact on the potential, attitudes, and behavior of civil servant organizations or agencies.

KEYWORDS: ANEKA Values, Attitudes and Behavior, CPNS Background.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of human resources is very important to accelerate progress in every profession (Sugian et al., 2021). In the context of managing human resources, education and training are very important things to do in order to create service excellence both in companies and government organizations (Man, 2020). The State Civil Apparatus (ASN) as a component of human resources, plays an important role in the development of the government system. The paradigm shift from "*rule governance*" to "*good governance*", must be addressed and balanced with apparatus resources with competencies, attitudes, and behaviors that are in accordance with public, national and global challenges (Subekan & Iskandar, 2019).

According to Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus (ASN), it is important to form ASN that has integrity, professionalism, neutrality, independence, and is free from political interference, as well as the ability to provide good public services to the community. Article 11 of the Law states that ASN (including civil servants) are responsible for: a) implementing public policies determined by the State Civil Apparatus in accordance with statutory regulations; b) provide professional and quality public services; and c) strengthen the unity and integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Civil servants who are able to carry out this role have competence as evidenced by their attitudes and behavior that are full of loyalty and obedience to the state, good morals and mentality, professionalism, awareness of their responsibilities as public servants, and able to become the glue of national unity and integrity. Coaching through training is important to develop a professional public servant figure as described above.

To be able to carry out their duties and roles in accordance with the mandate of Law Number 5 of 2014, every person who will be appointed as a Civil Servant must be educated and trained to have adequate qualifications so that civil servants are able to carry out

their duties with full responsibility. Education and training is a process that must be passed so that the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes of prospective Civil Servants (CPNS) can be formed so that they have the required competencies (Sriyatun, 2020). According to the Decree of the Head of the State Administration Agency (Kepka LAN) Number 93 of 2021 and Number 94 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Basic Training for Civil Servant Candidates, it is stated that the purpose of implementing basic training is to develop CPNS competencies. The CPNS competence in question is measured based on the ability to demonstrate state defense behavior, actualize the basic values of civil servants in carrying out their duties, actualize the position and role of civil servants within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI), and demonstrate mastery of the required technical competencies in accordance with their field of duty. For this reason, every CPNS is required to undergo a probationary period which is carried out through an integrated training process to build moral integrity, honesty, nationalism and nationalism spirit and motivation, superior and responsible personality character, and strengthen professionalism and field competence. Innovative and integrated basic training is needed to provide opportunities for participants to be able to internalize, apply, and actualize as well as habituate, feel the benefits, so that they are imprinted in themselves as professional Civil Servant characters according to their field of duty. Basic training and education that must be followed by Candidates for Civil Servants (Latsar CPNS) is the foundation for CPNS before carrying out their duties and positions. The CPNS Latsar is carried out to provide briefing to prospective civil servants so that after becoming a civil servant they can provide good and professional services. The implementation of the CPNS Latsar aims to shape the attitudes and behavior of civil servants so that they have the behavior of defending the country by reflecting the attitude of love for the homeland, awareness of the nation and state, believing in Pancasila as the state ideology, being willing to sacrifice for the nation and state, and having the initial ability to defend the country, and in accordance with with the basic values of civil servants, namely Accountability, Nationalism, Public Ethics, Quality Commitment, and Anti-Corruption (ANEKA). The behavior of defending the state and the basic values of civil servants should be implemented properly and correctly within the scope of the respective work units of Civil Servants.

Defending the State's behavior by reflecting ANEKA's values is an effort to change and shape the attitudes of CPNS Latsar participants so that they have attitudes and actions that are in accordance with applicable laws and regulations. ANEKA values are very important for ASN because each ASN is responsible for various policies, strategic decisions, development planning, and public services. Therefore, every ASN must be able to show attitudes and behaviors that are in accordance with the Basic values of Civil Servants in every word and deed to develop ASN who are responsible, professional, and have integrity. Based on the above background, this study aims to determine the effect of the implementation of the CPNS Latsar on the behavior of the CPNS Class 4 participants in Kerinci Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Basic Training of CPNS (Latsar)

According to the Regulation of the State Administration of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2021 concerning Basic Training of Civil Servant Candidates, it is stated that CPNS Basic Training is education and training in the Pre-service period which is carried out in an integrated manner to build moral integrity, honesty, enthusiasm, and nationalism and nationalism motivation, superior and responsible personality character, and strengthening professionalism and field competence. The competencies developed in the CPNS Latsar are competencies for forming professional civil servants' character in accordance with their respective fields of duty. This shows that as an ASN, civil servants are not only required to have knowledge of their duties and positions, but more than that they must have good behavior in providing public services to the community. The attitude and behavior of civil servants must reflect the basic values of civil servants as state defense behavior in carrying out their duties and responsibilities (Budiman, 2020). The superior personality character of a Civil Servant is very much needed in the midst of an increasingly globalized flow of globalization. The development of increasingly sophisticated technology has placed the world without borders (*borderless*), so that foreign influences will very easily enter and influence the attitudes and behavior of the Indonesian people, including the State Civil Apparatus (ASN). To face the challenges of globalization, it is necessary to strengthen the basic values of civil servants. Strengthening the basic values of civil servants for the sake of creating superior CPNS attitudes and behavior can be done through adaptive basic training for prospective civil servants as the formation of civil servant character and strengthening competence in accordance with the demands of their duties and positions. Based on the theoretical study above, it is concluded that CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) is needed in

forming Candidates for Civil Servants who have integrity, honesty, professionalism and can demonstrate an attitude of nationalism and reflect the basic values of civil servants in carrying out their duties and positions as public servants.

ANEKA

Values The basic values of civil servants contained in ANEKA are the basic values of the attitude and behavior of a civil servant that prioritizes Accountability, Nationalism, Public Ethics, Quality Commitment, and Anti-Corruption (LAN, 2019). ANEKA values are needed to form civil servants who can become role models as public servants with integrity and professionalism and are far from the actions and behavior of Corruption, Collusion, and Nepotism (KKN). *First*, Accountability, refers to the obligation of everyone, group, or institution to fulfill the mandated responsibilities. To create an accountable civil servant, there are 9 value indicators that must be possessed by a civil servant, namely responsibility, honesty, clarity of targets, neutral, prioritizing the public interest, fair, transparent, consistent, and participatory. Nine indicators of accountability values must be reflected in every civil servant attitude and behavior (LAN, 2019). *Second*, Nationalism is formulated as an understanding that creates and maintains the sovereignty of a country by realizing an identity as a common bond in a group. Nationalism is very important for every ASN employee (LAN, 2019). It's not even just insight, but the ability to actualize nationalism in carrying out its functions and duties is more important. With strong nationalism, it is hoped that every civil servant has an orientation to prioritize the interests of the public, nation and state. Indicators of the basic values of nationalism, among others; religious, trustworthy, disciplined, non-discriminatory, mutual respect, equality, loving fellow human beings, willing to sacrifice, maintaining order, cooperation, love for the homeland, deliberation, kinship, common interests, simple life, not using rights that do not belong to them, work hardworking, respecting the work of others, respecting shared decisions, and being considerate. *Third*, Public Ethics, is a reflection of standards or norms that determine good or bad, right or wrong behavior, actions and decisions to direct public policy in order to carry out public service responsibilities. The basic values of public ethics include upholding the values of the Pancasila ideology, being loyal to and defending the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, being professional, impartial, making decisions based on the principle of expertise, non-discrimination, having noble ethics, being accountable for their actions and performance to the public, providing services. honest, responsive, fast, precise and accurate, efficient and effective, polite in communicating, consulting and collaborating, transparent, prioritizing the achievement of results and encouraging employee performance, encouraging equality in work, and increasing the effectiveness of a democratic government system as a system tool. career (LAN, 2019). *Fourth*, Quality Commitment, a promise to ourselves or to others which is reflected in our actions to maintain the quality of employee performance. Any field that is the responsibility of civil servants must be carried out optimally in order to provide satisfaction to stakeholders. Quality commitment is an action to appreciate effectiveness, efficiency, innovation and quality-oriented performance in the administration of government and public services (LAN, 2019). Values that need to be considered in quality commitment include: working with quality-oriented, innovative, always making quality improvements, building employee commitment for the long term, building collegial cooperation between employees based on trust and honesty, focusing activities on customer satisfaction, both internally and externally, showing zero-defect and zero-waste performance, since starting every job, as well as being effective and efficient at work. *Fifth*, Anti-Corruption, which means not violating the law with the aim of enriching oneself and one's group. The values contained in the anti-corruption aspect include honest, caring, independent, disciplined, responsible, hard work, simple, brave, and fair (LAN, 2019).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method used in this study is a *mixed method*, namely qualitative and quantitative. The subjects of the research were the CPNS Latsar participants who were appointed to 4 Kerinci districts in 2021 with a total of 181 participants and the head of the Latsar work unit within the Kerinci district. Determination of research subjects is based on (a) the origin of the participating institutions covering the technical fields, teachers, and the health sector which are evenly distributed, so that the selected subjects represent all areas of government in Kerinci Regency; and (b) the working unit of the latsar participants covers the entire area of the Kerinci Regency, so that the selected subjects can represent the entire work area within the Kerinci Regency. Instruments of data collection were done through interview guide sheets, observation sheets, questionnaire sheets, and test sheets for CPNS Latsar participants. Quantitative data collection techniques were carried out through pretest and posttest activities. The pretest was carried out before giving treatment in the form of ANEKA values training, and the posttest was carried out after the Latsar participants were given knowledge and training about ANEKA values and the participants had been given the opportunity to implement the training lessons in their respective scopes

of work. Furthermore, qualitative data were collected using open questionnaires and interviews with the leaders of the Latsar participants after they returned to their respective work environments. Quantitative analysis was carried out by analyzing before and after the implementation of Basic Training (Latsar) through the *independent simple t test method*. The analysis of the independent simple t test aims to see whether there is a significant influence on the CPNS Latsar attitude and behavior on the Latsar participants. Statistical analysis was carried out using the SPSS version 25.0 computer program. To see the magnitude of the increase given by each variable, the N-Gain test was carried out. The criteria for the N-Gain scores are as follows:

Table 1. Criteria for the N-Gain score

Interval	Criteria
$g \geq 0.7$	High
$0.3 \leq g < 0.7$	Middle
$g < 0.3$	Low

While qualitative data analysis is carried out through triangulation which consists of from data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions (miles & Huberman, 1984).

RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

The impact or influence of CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) on changes in attitudes and behavior of the CPNS Class 4 Latsar participants in Kerinci Regency in 2021 were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative testing used *independent sample t test* to see if there was a significant influence on the CPNS training program on changes in attitudes and behavior of the CPNS participants. Before performing the t-test, prerequisite tests must first be carried out through normality tests and homogeneity tests to obtain data that are normally distributed and homogeneous. The normality test was carried out using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov technique, while the homogeneity test was carried out using the Levene's statistic test. The results of the normality test are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Normality test results

No.	Variable	Sig. (p-value)	Information
1	Accountability	0.574	Normal
2	Nationalism	0.677	Normal
3	Public Ethics	0.125	Normal
4	Quality Commitment	0.327	Normal
5	Anti-Corruption	0.231	Normal

Based on table 2, it is known that all data are normally distributed with a significance value for the five ANEKA values greater than 0,05. Furthermore, the results of the homogeneity test are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Homogeneity Test Result

		Levene Statistic	Sig.
Pretest	Based on Mean	2.175	.246
	Based on Median	3.467	.168
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	3.467	.168
	Based on trimmed mean	2.609	.212

Based on table 3, it is known that the homogeneity value is 0.246 (greater than 0.05) so it can be concluded that the distribution is homogeneous.

Based on the results of the prerequisite test, it is known that the data has met the prerequisites for the t test. Furthermore, the results of the t-test through the independent sample t-test are presented in table 4.

Table 4. t test results

Variabel	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	St. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Accountability	-19.592	180	0.000	-8.133	1.954	-8.980	-6.276
Nationalism	-18.642	180	0.000	-9.432	2.421	-4.526	-3.152
Public Ethics	-18.765	180	0.001	-7.452	2.431	-6.413	-4.632
Quality Commitment	-20.147	180	0.000	-8.435	1.874	-8.672	-7.517
Anti-Corruption	-18.411	180	0.001	-7.231	1.952	-7.347	-6.113

Based on table 4, it is known that the variables Accountability, Nationalism, and Quality commitment have a significance value of 0.000 and the variables Public Ethics and Anti-Corruption has a significance value of 0.001. Based on these results, it is known that the five ANEKA values have a significance value less than 0.05. The findings of the study indicate that there is a significant effect on the implementation of CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) on the attitudes and behavior of Latsar 4 Kerinci Regency participants in 2021. This is confirmed by the t-test values for the 5 ANEKA values variables which show scores below 0, 05. The results of qualitative research also show the same thing, that the CPNS Latsar has a significant effect on attitudes and behavior as well as the potential of each participant in providing public services. The findings of this study support several research results (for example, Junjuna, 2020; Subekan & Iskandar, 2019) that the Civil Service Candidate Training Center has a positive and significant effect on the implementation of ANEKA values by Latsar participants in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as public servants. This means that the CPNS Latsar has been able to change the attitudes and behavior of the trainees for the better.

Furthermore, to see how much influence is given by each variable, then the N-Gain test is carried out. The N-Gain value of each variable can be seen in figure 1.

Based on figure 1, it is known that on average each variable has an influence on the behavior of the CPNS Latsar participants by 51.84% in the medium category. Figure 1 shows that the biggest influence of CPNS Latsar activities has an impact on the quality commitment of participants, which is 62.10%. These results indicate that after attending basic training, each participant of the CPNS Latsar is able to improve the quality of their performance by working in accordance with their respective duties and functions and being able to use time and energy as efficiently as possible, so as to achieve the targets that have been set. In addition, each Latsar participant is also able to provide new innovations in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in their respective work units. The CPNS Latsar activity also has a considerable influence on the accountability value of 53.20%. Accountability is very important because it is one of the three pillars of *good governance* (Septiani & Kusumastuti, 2019). In addition, accountability has three main functions, namely (1) to provide democratic control; (2) to prevent corruption and abuse of power; (3) to increase efficiency and effectiveness (Dhahri et al., 2017).

The next variable is Public Ethics. Public ethics is an important aspect as a reference in carrying out the duties of the government and its apparatus, in providing services to the community good ethics are needed so that superior and professional services can be realized, and the Indonesian nation is able to fight for its independence by increasing welfare for all people. The values of public ethics are important elements that must be considered to realize *good governance* in achieving development goals, namely increasing people's welfare. The next variable is the value of Nationalism. Nationalism is very important to be possessed by an ASN as a guardian of state sovereignty, to become a unifier of the nation, to strive for a peaceful situation throughout Indonesia, and to maintain the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

This is in accordance with the function of civil servants as glue and unifying the nation and state, so that every ASN employee must have a strong spirit of nationalism. While the lowest effect is displayed on the anti-corruption value, which is 45.70%. Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that anti-corruption attitudes still need to be improved in civil servants. However, it can be concluded that the CPNS Latsar activities have a positive effect on the potential, attitudes, and behavior of the organization or agency of a civil servant.

In line with the results of quantitative research, the results of qualitative research also show a positive influence after providing basic training to participants of Latsar CPNS Batch 4 Kerinci Regency on the attitudes and behavior of participants in providing good public services, communicating effectively with superiors, colleagues, and government authorities. Based on the results of interviews with the leadership of the training unit participants, it was stated that employees who took part in the training were able to demonstrate high discipline (arrival on time, dress modestly, accuracy and speed in completing tasks, take responsibility for the assigned tasks, work professionally (correctly, quickly), but still careful and thorough), prioritizing the public interest over personal interests, generating creative and innovative ideas for the advancement of the organization and work units. The behavior shown by the participants of the CPNS Latsar Batch 4 Kerinci Regency is much different than before being included in the CPNS Latsar. After following the CPNS Latsar, participants showed attitudes and behavior that were much more in line with the expected behavior as

professional CPNS. Based on the above discussion, it was concluded that the CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) for CPNS had a significant impact on the attitudes and behavior of Latsar 4 Kerinci participants in 2021.

CONCLUSION

The research findings show that there is a significant effect on the implementation of CPNS Basic Training (Latsar) on the attitudes and behavior of Latsar Batch 4 Kerinci Regency participants in 2021. This is confirmed by the t-test values for the 5 ANEKA values variables which show the scores at below 0.05. CPNS Latsar activities have a good impact on the potential, attitudes, and behavior of civil servant organizations or agencies. Each participant is also able to demonstrate high discipline (arrival on time, dress modestly, do work properly and quickly, be responsible for the responsibilities assigned, prioritize the public interest above individual interests).

REFERENCES

1. Budiman, A. (2020). Strengthening the Attitude of Integrity Through Basic Training of Civil Servant Candidates. *Teaching and Learning: Journal of Educational Science Research*, 3(2), 275-282.
2. Dhahri, I., Kasmawati, A., & Bakhtiar, B. Understanding of Basic Professional Values and Work Culture of State Civil Apparatus in the Faculty of Social Sciences, Makassar State University. *SUPREMASI: Journal of Thought, Research in the Social Sciences, Law and Its Teaching*, 12(2), 90-104.
3. Institute of State Administration of the Republic of Indonesia. (2021). Decree of the Head of the State Administration Number: 93/K.1/PDP.07/2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of the Training of Candidates for Civil Servants.
4. Junjunan, BA (2020). Evaluation of Learning Various Values and Their Influence on the Behavior of Alumni Latsar CPNS. *Scientific Journal of Batanghari University Jambi*, 20(3), 946-951.
5. Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus
6. Man, S. (2020). Analysis of the Role of Education and Training in Improving Employee Performance. *Accounting*, 6(1), 38-45.
7. RI LAN Regulation Number 1 of 2021 concerning Basic Training of Civil Servant Candidates
8. Septiani, S., & Kusumastuti, E. (2019, August). Application of Non-Cash Transactions in the Implementation of Local Government Expenditures to Realize the Principles of Good Governance (Case Study on the Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency of the West Java Provincial Government). In *Proceedings of Industrial Research Workshop and National Seminar* (Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 1171-1181).
9. Sriyatun, S. (2020). Study of the Implementation of the Basic Values of Nationalist Civil Servants in Participants After the 2019 CPNS Regional Research Center BPSDM Central Java Province. *Journal of Sipatokkong BPSDM South Sulawesi*, 1(2), 154-169.
10. State Administration Institute. (2019). Basic Training Module for Candidates for Civil Servants Category II and Category III: Accountability. Jakarta: State Administration Institute.
11. State Administration Institute. (2019). Basic Training Module for Candidates for Civil Servants Class II and Class III: Public Ethics. Jakarta: State Administration Institute.
12. State Administration Institute. (2019). Basic Training Module for Candidates for Civil Servants Category II and Category III: Quality Commitment. Jakarta: State Administration Institute.
13. State Administration Institute. (2019). Basic Training Module for Candidates for Civil Servants Class II and Class III: Anti-Corruption. Jakarta: State Administration Institute.
14. State Administration Institute. (2021). Decree of the Head of the State Administration Number 94/K.1/PDP.07/2021 concerning the Basic Training Curriculum for Candidates for Civil Servants.
15. State Administrative Institution. (2019). Basic Training Module for Candidates for Civil Servants Category II and Category III: Nationalism. Jakarta: State Administration Institute.

16. Subekan, A., & Iskandar, A. (2019). The Influence of Understanding the Basic Values of 'ANEKA' on the Attitude Formation of Civil Servant Latsar Participants at the Malang Financial Education and Training Center. *Journal of Education*, 20(2), 91-110.
17. Sugian, S., Lukman, S., & Wargadinata, EL (2021). Strategy to Improve the Quality of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) Resources in Sumedang Regency, West Java Province (Study at BKPSDM Sumedang Regency). *VISIONER: Journal of Regional Government in Indonesia*, 13(3), 555-582.

Cite this Article: Asnofidal, Hamid Majid (2022). Impact of CPNS Latsar on Changes in Behavioral Attitudes of Latsar Participants for the 4th Kerinci District in 2021. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(4), 1280-1287